

KVANT NAZARIYASINING TABIATDAGI TALQINI.

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ANNOSTATSIYA.

Klassik fizika va kvant nazariyasi o'rtasidagi munosabatlar fizika falsafasi uchun markaziy ahamiyatga ega va kvant mexanikasining har qanday talqini bu munosabatni aniqlashtirishi kerak. Gravitatsiyadan tashqari, kvant mexanikasi deyarli barcha ma'lum bo'lgan hodisalarni, atomlarning tuzilishi, kimyo va kondensatsiyalangan moddalardan yadro tuzilishi va elementar zarralar fizikasigacha tushuntiradi. Bularning barchasini misli ko'rilmagan aniqlik bilan bajaradi. Ammo kashf etilganidan deyarli 90 yil o'tgach, biz hali ham o'lchov muammosi bilan bo'lgani kabi, kvant mexanikasi haqida ham chuqur tushunchaga ega emasmiz, degan umumiy kelishuv mavjud. G'oyalar va usullarning kombinatsiyasi o'lchov muammosini to'liq hal qilmaydi, lekin klassik vaziyat ba'zi holatlar va kvant nazariyasi kuzatilishi mumkin bo'lgan narsalarni yo'q qilish natijasida paydo bo'lishini ta'kidlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar:kvant nazariyasi,gravitatsiya,elementar zarralar.

Kvant nazariyasi ham hayotimizni ta'minlovchi zamonaviy texnologiyalarning asosini tashkil etadi. Zamonaviy hisoblash texnikasining asosini tashkil etuvchi tranzistorni loyihalash va modellashtirish uchun kvant nazariyasi talab qilinadi. Xuddi shu narsa optik aloqa tarmoqlari (telekommunikatsiya sanoatining asosi) va optik ma'lumotlarni saqlash (masalan, CD va DVD diskleri) ning asosini tashkil etuvchi lazer va yorug'lik diodiga ham tegishli. Ilg'or kvant kompyuterlari va kvant shifrlash kabi texnologiyalar ham hayotimizga tez kirib bormoqda. Kvant nazariyasining eksperimental muvaffaqiyatlari tufayli kvant nazariyasining matematik qoidalari jismoniy dunyo faoliyatining asosiy xususiyatlarini to'g'ri aks ettirishiga shubha yo'q. To'qson yil oldin tuzilganidan beri, bu qoidalar klassik fizikaning asosini tashkil etuvchi voqelik nuqtai nazaridan saqlanishi mumkin bo'lmagan jismoniy voqelikni tasvirlaydigan juda kuchli belgilar mavjud edi. Biroq, moddiy dunyoni tushunishda kvant formalizmining aniq tabiati noaniqligicha qolmoqda. Kvant fizikasi klassik fizikadan farqli o'laroq, fizik tizimlarni modellashtirish uchun qo'llanilishi mumkin bo'lgan matematik asosga ega. Ushbu vaziyat qanday sodir bo'lganini tushunish uchun ba'zi tarixiy yondashuvlarni ko'rib chiqish foydali bo'ladi. Nyuton mexanikasi Yerdagi jismlarning harakatini ham, sayyoralar, oylar va

kometalarning orbitalarini batafsil astronomik kuzatishlarini ham tushuntirib berdi; Maksvell elektromagnetizmi elektr va magnit hodisalarini (jumladan, yorug'lik hodisasini miqdoriy tushuntirish) har tomonlama tushunish imkonini berdi va termodinamika, issiqlik hodisasi va issiqlikni foydali mexanik harakatga aylantirish jarayoni haqida batafsil ma'lumot berdi. Biroq, ba'zi bir savol belgilari ham bor edi: bu nazariyalarga o'jarlik bilan qarshilik ko'rsatadigan empirik faktlar mavjud edi. Ushbu faktlardan biri qizdirilgan ob'ektlar tomonidan chiqarilgan yorug'lik chastotalari bilan bog'liq edi (klassik nazariyalar hatto tajriba ma'lumotlarini sifat jihatidan ham hisobga olmadi). Bu faktlarga (Maks Plank tashabbusi bilan) berilgan vaqtinchalik tushuntirishlar klassik fizikaning matematik asosini almashtiradigan fizik nazariyalar uchun mutlaqo yangi nazariy asos bo'lgan kvant nazariyasining rivojlanishiga olib keladi.

ADABIYOTLAR TAHLILI VA METODOLOGIYA

Kvant nazariyasidagi bu klassik bo'lmagan xususiyatlarni yoritish uchun ba'zi fiziklar mavjud tushunchalarni sharhlashga yoki yangi tushunchalarni ishlab chiqishga harakat qildilar, ularda bu xususiyatlar o'ziga xos misollar sifatida qabul qilinishi mumkin va shu bilan klassik bo'lmagan xususiyatlarni o'z ichiga oladi. Masalan, Bor to'ldiruvchilik tushunchasini ishlab chiqdi. Ushbu kontseptsiyaga ko'ra;

- Har qanday tajribada eksperimental asboblari va kuzatishning ishtirok etish jarayonini an'anaviy tushunchalar bilan tushuntirib bo'lmaydi.
- Eksperimental jarayon davomida kuzatish va kuzatilayotgan narsa o'rtasida aniq chegara o'tkazib bo'lmaydi; chunki kuzatish jarayoni kuzatilayotgan narsaga ta'sir qiladi.
- Atom dunyosini tasvirlash uchun to'lqin va zarracha kabi tushunchalar qo'llanilishi muqarrar, ammo har xil eksperimental vaziyatlar uchun turli modellardan foydalanish kerak. Ushbu turli xil modellar va vaziyatlarni "qarama-qarshi" deb emas, balki "bir-birini to'ldiruvchi" sifatida ko'rish kerak, chunki ular bir xil eksperimental sharoitlarda paydo bo'lmaydi. (Masalan, elektron bir eksperimental holatda zarracha, boshqasida to'lqindir.)

Hozirda bizda kvant nazariyasini qo'llab-quvvatlaydigan voqelik haqida tushuncha yo'qligi sababli, kvant nazariyasi asos bo'lgan moddiy dunyoning xususiyatlari noma'lum. Kengroq ma'noda fanlararo nuqtai nazardan, kvant nazariyasining asosini tashkil etuvchi voqelikni tushunmaslik kvant nazariyasining mohiyati fanning boshqa sohalariga va kengroq aytganda, boshqa

sohalarga to'g'ri kelmasligini bildiradi. Garchi bu usullar muhim ma'lumot bergan bo'lsa-da, ularning asosiy cheklovi kvant nazariyasidan ma'lum bir tarzda foydalanishidir. Klassik fizika tabiiy ravishda matematiklashtirilsa, inson haqiqatni aniq tushunadi. Biroq, kvant formalizmi klassik fizika asosidagi matematik asosda topilmaydigan ko'plab matematik konstruktsiyalarga ega. Masalan, tizimlarning holatlari kompleks vektor fazoda kompleks vektorlar bilan, holatlarning vaqtinchalik evolyutsiyasi esa bu vektorlarning unitar transformatsiyalari bilan ifodalanadi. Ehtimol, bu holatning jismoniy sabablari bor, ammo bu sabablar nima? Yuqorida tilga olingan kvant nazariyasini yechish harakatlari bu savolga javob bera olmaydi.

Xulosa.

So'nggi yillarda kvant nazariyasida g'oyalarning mosligini aniqlashga harakat qilish kerakligi tushunildi. Ya'ni, nazariyani ma'lum bir tarzda qabul qilishdan ko'ra, kvant nazariyasini olish mumkin bo'lgan oddiy tamoyillarni shakllantirish ustida ishlash kerak. Kvant nazariyasini shu tarzda qayta qurish kvant nazariyasining fizik mazmunini tabiiy tilda ifodalangan aniq ifodalar to'plamiga o'tkazadi; Shunday qilib, kvant nazariyasining butun mazmuni zarur kontseptual tahlil uchun mavjud bo'ladi. Natijada, kvant nazariyasini turli xil boshlang'ich nuqtalarga asoslangan batafsil qayta qurish davom etmoqda. Biroq, hozirgacha mavjud ishlarning hech biri mavhum matematik taxminlarni kiritmasdan kvant nazariyasini standart shaklda ololmadi. Berilgan tajribada olingan har bir o'lchov natijalari ketma-ketligi haqiqiy sonlar juftligi bilan ifodalanadi va bu ketma-ketlikning har ikkala komponentining funksiyasini bajarish ehtimoli uzluksiz emas. Simmetriya va konsistensiyaning asosiy shartlaridan foydalanib, va shunday deb faraz qilmasdan, bu juft haqiqiy sonlar boshqa algebraik tuzilishga ega emas, bu juftliklar uni murakkab arifmetik qoidalarga muvofiq manipulyatsiya qilish kerakligi aniqlandi. Bundan tashqari, ushbu kompleks raqamlar Feynmanning yig'indisi qoidalariga bo'ysunishi aniqlandi, bu modullar kvadrati bilan birlashtirilib, natijalar ketma-ketligi ehtimolini beradi. Yondashuvning mohiyatini tashkil etuvchi ikki tomonlama taxmin jismoniy tizimda o'tkazilgan o'lchov faqat tizim erkinlik darajalarining yarmi haqida ma'lumot berishi mumkin degan fikrni ifodalaydi. Bu Bor tomonidan yaratilgan to'ldiruvchilik printsiplarining rasmiylashtirilishi. Klassik mexanikada zarrachaga bir vaqtning o'zida joylashuv va tezlikning aniq qiymatlari berilishi mumkin deb taxmin qilinadi. Biroq, kvant nazariyasining taxmini shundan iboratki, bir vaqtning o'zida pozitsiyaning aniq qiymatini yoki tezlik xususiyatlarini ko'rsatish mumkin, lekin ikkalasini ham emas.

Fundamental klassik kontseptsiyadagi ushbu kvant cheklovini tushunish uchun Bor "To'ldiruvchilik printsiplari" ni ishlab chiqdi. Ushbu printsiplarga ko'ra, fizik hodisaning har qanday tavsifi ma'lum bir empirik tartibga solish bilan chambarchas bog'liq bo'lib, bunday tartibga solish klassik tafakkurda hodisani to'liq tavsiflash uchun bir xil darajada zarur bo'lgan hodisaning boshqa tomonlarini istisno qilish uchun ishlatiladi. Kier Kegaard falsafiy tafakkurining dialektik jihatidan qisman ilhomlangan bu tamoyil umumiy falsafiy tamoyilning alohida holatidir. Prinsiplarning umumiylikni kashf qilib, Bor va boshqalar aqliy va organik sohalaridagi o'xshash hodisalarni ko'rsatdilar. Masalan, Pauli jismoniy to'ldiruvchilik va aqliy tajribaning ongsiz va ongli tomonlari o'rtasidagi munosabat o'rtasidagi o'xshashlikni ishlab chiqdi. Zamonaviy psixologiya esa ongsiz psixikaning asosan ob'ektiv realligini ochib beradi; ularning har biri ongni, ya'ni kuzatishni keltirib chiqaradi, printsiplarning jihatidan nazorat qilib bo'lmaydigan ongsiz mazmun bilan o'zaro ta'sirni tashkil qiladi; Bu holat ongsiz voqelikning ob'ektiv xarakterini cheklaydi va voqelikni ma'lum bir sub'ektivlik bilan ajratib turadi.

Maqola doirasida ikkita asosiy taxmin qilingan. Birinchidan, noaniqlikning operativ taxmini mavjud, ya'ni ehtimollik o'lchovlarga xosdir. Ikkinchidan, to'ldiruvchilik ma'lum bir tajribada tizimni nazariy tavsiflash uchun zarur bo'lgan erkinlik darajasining faqat yarmiga erishish mumkinligini o'z ichiga oladi. Ushbu ikkala taxmin ham klassik fizikaning mexanik nuqtai nazaridan noaniqlik (o'lchov natijasi tizimning holati bilan belgilanadi) va asosiy tamoyillar (ya'ni, printsiplarning ravishda, erishish mumkin bo'lgan bitta mezon mavjud) bilan tizimning erkinlik darajalaridir. hammasi). Agar noaniqlik va bir-birini to'ldiruvchilik berilgan deb qabul qilinsa, tabiatni qanday tushunish taklif qilinadi? Kvant nazariyasini qayta qurish, yuqorida tasvirlanganidek, yangi "Tabiat tushunchasi" yo'lidagi muhim ishdir, chunki u bizning e'tiborimizni faqat oz sonli noklassik bo'lmagan xususiyatlarga qaratadi, lekin u hali ham bir pog'onadir.

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